

NEW TEMPERATURES IN DOMINEERING

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Abstract

Games of No Chance [8] presents a table of known Domineering temperatures, including approximately 40 with denominator less than or equal to 512, and poses the challenge of finding new temperatures. We present 219 Domineering positions with distinct temperatures not shown in *GONC* – including 26 with temperature greater than $3/2$ – obtained through exhaustive computational search of several Domineering grid sizes.

1. Background

In the game of *Domineering* [7, 3], players Left and Right alternate placing dominoes on a finite grid of arbitrary size or shape. Left places her dominoes vertically, and Right horizontally. Play continues until a player cannot move; that player is the loser. In spite of its apparent simplicity, many of the properties of combinatorial games can be expressed in Domineering [3].

Analyzing general Domineering positions, *i.e.*, finding their canonical values and temperatures, is difficult. Early work exhaustively analyzed positions of very small size [3]. Since then, inroads have been made for positions with repetitive patterns, such as snakes [13, 9] and $x \times y$ rectangles for particular values of x [1]. There is preliminary work on determining which player can win for rectangular boards of increasingly large dimensions [4, 10], but no comprehensive analysis has been performed on these boards. Because of the complexity of analyzing Domineering positions, much about the values and temperatures of arbitrary Domineering positions remains unknown.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -1, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{4}, -\frac{1}{8}, \dots \\
 & 0, \frac{1}{8}, \frac{3}{16}, \frac{7}{32}, \dots \\
 & \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{8}, \frac{7}{16}, \frac{15}{32}, \dots \\
 & \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{7}{8}, \frac{15}{16}, \dots \\
 & 1, 1\frac{1}{8}, 1\frac{3}{16}, 1\frac{1}{4}, 1\frac{5}{16}, 1\frac{11}{32}
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 1: Previously known temperatures in Domineering as presented in [8].

Figure 1: A Domineering position with several left and right options.

Games of No Chance [8] presents a table of known Domineering temperatures, seen in Table 1, including approximately 40 with denominator less than or equal to 512. *GONC* then poses the challenge of finding new temperatures. Since the publication of *GONC*, Gabriel Drummond-Cole discovered a position of temperature 2 and several others with temperatures between $3/2$ and 2 [5]; however, we know of no other published results presenting new Domineering temperatures.

A computational search technique was successfully applied to other games such as Fox and Geese [12]; we are not aware of previous work that applies exhaustive search to Domineering.

Figure 2: A Domineering position whose canonical form has more than 20,000 characters.

2. New Temperatures

We modified version 0.3 of Aaron Siegel's CGSuite tool [11] to enumerate all Domineering positions that can be fit into boards of dimensions 5×6 , 4×8 , 3×10 , and 2×16 , recording positions with unique temperatures¹. The computation resulted in the discovery of 219 new temperatures, including 26 with temperature greater than $3/2$, all with a denominator of 512 or less. These new temperatures are particularly exciting since they occur on positions small enough to arise in tournament play; some more esoteric temperatures found in previous work occurred on less common positions of larger dimensions. We also found 40 additional temperatures in *generalized Domineering*, in which the position is not necessarily reachable through gameplay from an empty rectangular grid.

Our search of over 10 billion positions found no position with temperature greater than 2. Elywn Berlekamp has long sought a proof of a maximum temperature in Domineering [2], and while our technique cannot provide such a proof, it lends credence to the current belief that 2 is the largest possible temperature in Domineering.

Among the grids that we searched, we have found all temperatures between 0 and 2 with denominator 16, all but two with denominator 32, all but 15 with denominator 64, and so on². An open question is whether every dyadic rational temperature between 0 and 2 is achievable given a sufficiently large Domineering position.

3. Additional Analysis

Our exhaustive computational search complements previous approaches to analyzing Domineering positions in its ability to handle arbitrary positions, rather than just those that fit some pattern. Previous work exploited patterns in empty rectangular boards [1, 4, 10] or repetitive non-rectangular patterns [13, 9] to generalize and ease the analysis process. Our technique finds and evaluates irregular Domineering positions that do not easily fit into such patterns and seem quite difficult to analyze by hand – but that still have interesting values and temperatures.

For example, we encountered millions of distinct Domineering *values* in our search for new temperatures, 80% of which had multiple options. Figure 1 presents an example of one such interesting Domineering position³, with eight canonical left options and seven canonical right options. Note that left only has 13 choices for a move, and right only 15; over half are canonical choices for play. It is rare to find so many undominated options in such a small

¹The modifications are available as a CGSuite plugin; email the authors if interested.

²Gabriel Drummond-Cole has since found positions with the two temperatures with denominator 32, $61/32$ and $63/32$. Our search did not find these positions because they do not fit into the board sizes we searched[6].

³The canonical form of this position was too large to print; it can be found by entering the position into CGSuite [11].

Figure 3: A Domineering position whose value is $+_{5/2}$.

position. We also found many positions with large and complex canonical forms, the largest of which (seen in Figure 2) had more than 20,000 characters.

We have also discovered a variety of positions with tiny and miny values; few positions with such values are known in Domineering [2]. The values our search encountered include $+_{1/4}$, $+_{1/2}$, $+_{3/4}$, $+_1$, $+_{3/2}$, $+_2$, $+_{5/2}$ and their starred equivalents (e.g. $+_{1/2*}$), as well as other more complex tiny values. Figure 3 shows a position with value $+_{5/2}$.

Our exhaustive search can easily be modified to output any information about the discovered positions, such as thermographs, chilled values of positions, etc.

Section 4 presents the standard Domineering positions with new temperatures that we found, and Section 5 presents the generalized positions.

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4. Standard Positions

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	7/64						
	19/64						
	23/64						
	29/64						
	35/64						
	39/64						
	41/64						
	11/16						

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	23/32						
	193/256						
	25/32						
	13/16						
	107/128						
	111/128						
	229/256						
	235/256						

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	121/128						
	125/128						
	65/64						
	33/32						
	67/64						
	17/16						
	275/256						
	279/256						

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	563/512						
	285/256						
	575/512						
	291/256						
	293/256						
	37/32						
	75/64						
	305/256						

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	309/256						
	39/32						
	79/64						
	321/256						
	325/256						
	329/256						
	333/256						
	169/128						

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	339/256		85/64		341/256		171/128
	343/256		345/256		173/128		347/256
	87/64		349/256		175/128		351/256
	177/128		355/256		89/64		357/256
	179/128		45/32		361/256		181/128
	91/64		183/128		23/16		369/256
	185/128		371/256		93/64		187/128
	47/32		189/128		95/64		191/128

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	195/128						
	25/16						
	103/64						
	107/64						
	7/4						
	15/8						
	2						

5. Generalized Positions

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	65/128						
	77/128						
	215/256						
	227/256						
	247/256						
	541/512						
	601/512						
	359/256						

Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.	Position	Temp.
	197/128						
	113/64						

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